

Macroskills of Grade Five Learners in Selected Schools of Santa Maria District

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ABSTRACT

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The study aimed to assess the macroskills of grade five learners in selected schools of Santa Maria District, Division of Ilocos Sur during the Academic Year 2024-2025. It specifically determined the profile of the respondents along gender, educational attainment of their parents, available gadgets, and available reading materials. Specifically, the aim of this study is to determine the significant relationship between the profile of the respondents and the pupils' level of macroskills. Further, it aimed to identify the skills of grade five learners that are needed to address.

The study employed descriptive and correlational research design. A total of 49 grade five learners of the three selected schools of Santa Maria District serve as the respondents of the study. The research instrument of this study is divided into parts, first is the pupil's profile, and the second is the activities to assess the level of the macroskills of the respondents. The activities are adopted under the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) 2018 for Grades Five of Department of Education with additional reading activities made by the researcher. The statistical treatment used to treat the data was spearman rank correlation.

Findings revealed that in terms of the profile of the respondents, male and female respondents were not equal; female are more dominant which is 30 than male respondents which is 19. Most of the mothers of the respondents are highschool graduate which is 23 or 46.9% and only 2 finished their doctoral degree. Most of the fathers of the respondents are college graduate which is 22 or 44.9% while 8 graduated in elementary. Most of the respondents have available gadgets in their home which can they can use to enhance their macroskills. Likewise, respondents have available reading materials that can aid to the development of their macroskills. The respondents had obtained a descriptive rating of "excellent" both in their reading and listening skills while respondents had obtained a descriptive rating of "very good" both in their speaking and writing skills. As regards to the relationship between the profile of the respondents and the level of macroskills of the grade five learners, gender has a significant relationship with their speaking skill. The educational attainment of the parents of respondents has a significant relationship with their speaking skill. In terms of available gadgets of the respondents in their home, there's an inversely relationship between basic cellphone and with their speaking skill. There is also inverse relationship between smartphone to the reading skill of the respondents. There's a significant relationship between tablet and the writing skill of the respondents. In terms of the available reading materials of the respondents, it shows that there is an inverse relationship between the speaking skill of the respondents with their listening skill. Based on the results gathered, it is found out that the listening and reading skills of the respondents are more developed compared to their speaking and writing skill. Most of respondents in writing skills are found to struggle with basic grammar, have limited vocabulary and difficulty in paragraph development while in their speaking skill, respondents are observed to have weakness to speak in front because of having limited vocabulary and pronunciation anxiety.

Based on the above-cited findings and the results of the conducted study, the following are hereby recommended, first, the teacher must provide more guidance to the parents especially in developing the macroskills of the learners. Parents or any member of the family should provide an ample time to the learners to guide them and teach them at home.

Second, the teacher should create and implement more learning interventions in order to help those learners who are struggling in developing their macroskills. Teachers should continue giving and providing learners enrichment activities to further develop their skills in listening, speaking, reading and writing. Additionally, grade five teachers shall continue to develop professionally by attending seminars and trainings that relevant to the development of the macroskills of the grade five learners. Teachers must address immediately the learning difficulties of learners to avoid worst cases that could result on learning disorders.

Keywords: Grade Five Learners, Macroskills, Development, Reading Skill, Writing Skill, Speaking Skill, Listening Skill

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CHAPTER ONE INTRODUCTION

A. *Background of the Study*

In the intricate tapestry of human communication and language acquisition, the macroskills stand as the pillars upon which our ability to interact with the world is built. These essential abilities, namely listening, speaking, reading, and writing are the cornerstones of our capacity to understand, express, and navigate the vast sea of information that surrounds us.

Listening, the first of these skills, is often underestimated but is the gateway to comprehension. It's the art of not only hearing words but truly understanding their meaning, tone, and context. Proficiency in listening enables individuals to engage in meaningful dialogues, absorb knowledge, and foster empathetic connections with others.

The role of listening covers various aspects of listening, including active listening and the importance of listening in different communication settings. Technology and communication trends has influence the way we listen and communicate (Wolvin & Coakley, 2000).

One of the problem inside the classroom is student susceptibility to distractions, both internal and external. This can significantly hinder their ability to listen attentively.

In culturally diverse classrooms, language barriers can impede students' ability to comprehend spoken instructions and lectures. This can lead to reduce academic performance (Yates & Marcelo, 2020).

The way teachers deliver information can impact students' listening comprehension. Teachers who speak too quickly, use complex language, or do not provide sufficient pauses for processing can create difficulties for students (Lundeberg et al., 2016).

Speaking, the counterpart to listening, allows us to communicate our thoughts, ideas, and emotions. Through spoken language, we share our perspectives, engage in debates, and establish our identities in the world. It is the bridge that connects our inner thoughts to the external universe.

Speaking, a quintessential facet of human interaction, is a dynamic and multifaceted skill that transcends mere words. It is the art of vocalizing thoughts, emotions, and ideas, weaving a tapestry of communication that connects individuals across cultures, generations, and time. Speaking is both an intricate science, with its linguistic nuances and cognitive intricacies, and an art, express through the cadence, tone, and inflection of our voices. The art of speaking is a force that not only shapes our personal and professional lives but also defines the contours of our shared human experience.

On the other hand, the prevalence of technology in the classroom can be a double-edged sword. While technology can enhance communication, it can also become a source of distraction, with students using devices for non-academic purposes during speaking activities (Beland & Murphy, 2016).

Moving beyond the spoken word, reading emerges as a skill of paramount importance. Reading is the vessel that transports us into the realms of knowledge and imagination. It empowers us to explore the wisdom of the past, the discoveries of the present, and the possibilities of the future. Proficient readers can decipher complex texts, analyze information critically, and gain insights that shape their own perspectives.

Silva and Cain (2015) summarize the reading process as readers decoding words and retrieving their meaning, applying their syntactic knowledge to combine these into larger units— such as clauses and sentences—and integrating information across different parts of the text.

In the 2018 Program for International Student Assessment (PISA), the Philippines scored lowest in Reading out 79 countries that participated. It is shown in the results of the PISA that only one out of five Filipino learners aged 15 has achieve at least the minimum proficiency level in Overall Reading Literacy.

In the digital age, learners are often bombarded with vast amounts of information from various sources. This can lead to information overload and difficulties in discerning credible sources from unreliable ones (Baron, 2015).

Lastly, the ability to write is the mirror image of reading. Writing is the means by which we codify our thoughts and ideas, preserving them for posterity. Whether it's crafting a persuasive essay, composing a heartfelt letter, or simply jotting down personal reflections, writing allows us to articulate our innermost musings and share them with a broader audience.

Writing is a timeless and indispensable skill that plays a pivotal role in human communication and progress. It is the art of expressing thoughts, ideas, and emotions through the written word, creating a lasting record of our imagination, knowledge, and creativity. Writing is a versatile and invaluable skill that empowers individuals to communicate effectively, think critically, and contribute to the exchange of ideas and knowledge. It is not only a practical tool for academic and professional success but also a means of personal expression and a force for positive change in the world.

Students often struggle with grammar, punctuation, and spelling, which can detract from the overall quality of their writing (Hunt & Beglar, 2005). Many learners have difficulty organizing their thoughts and structuring their writing in a clear and coherent manner (Graham & Perin, 2007).

A limited vocabulary can restrict learners' ability to express themselves precisely and eloquently in writing (Baumann & Kame'enui, 2004). In culturally diverse classrooms, learners from different linguistic backgrounds may face challenges in adapting to the conventions of academic writing in a new language (Matsuda & Tardy, 2007).

To explore the macroskills, we delve into the essence of human communication and cognition. These skills are the instruments through which we decipher language and express thoughts. Each skill, like a note, contributes to the harmonious and multifaceted melody of human interaction and understanding. As we delve deeper into the significance of these skills, we can unlock effective communications, lifelong learning, and personal growth.

Today, the recent pandemic affects most of the learners of Santa Maria District. Based on observations, intermediate learners are lagging behind their grade level. Learners cannot cope with new lessons as they cannot understand or comprehend the topic. Despite interventions, some learners are not particularly improved by these interventions. Realizing and compelling need of learners with regards to their macroskills, this motivates the researcher to determine the level of Grade Five learners of selected schools in Santa Maria District with regards to their macroskills. It is hoped that the results can help the researcher come up with an innovation for the macroskill of Grade Five learners of Santa Maria District.

The current study is based on this vital need.

B. Framework of the Study

Nowadays, the macroskills of the Grade Five learners are seen to be deteriorating. However, various methods are used to help Grade Five learners to enhance their macroskills. For instance, the use of games to enhance their macroskills, wherein games play a significant role in education. Applying game-design elements and mechanics to non-game contexts to increase motivation and engagement (Young, Slota, Cutter, Jalette, Mullin, Lai, ... & Yukhymenko, 2012).

Listening effectively is not a matter of simply hearing what someone has to say. It is an important skill that must be honed and maintained. Listening skills provide a great competitive advantage when it comes to job selection, with a great listener being set above the rest due to their ability to absorb and process information, then respond accordingly. Faulty listening skills have the potential to lead to misunderstood assignments, misinterpreted conversational tones, and even affect the relationship between subordinates and superiors.

The HURIER model (Brownell 1996) provides a comprehensive framework for understanding the listening process. The six letters in the HURIER model represent the six interlock listening process: (1) Hearing or the physical reception of sound. It involves not only the accurate reception of sounds, but focus, discrimination between sounds and concentration on the information. Hearing is a constant part of daily life, as it becomes more important in social interactions, as information being portrayed must first be heard to be understood; (2) Understanding or the process of comprehending the meaning of the message. It is a matter of listening comprehension and setting the stage for the rest of the interaction, especially when it comes to interpreting, evaluating, and responding; (3) Remembering, the ability to retain or recall information. It is vital to retain information as to recall past experiences in order to properly utilize information; (4) Interpreting or assigning the meaning and context to the message. Taking the context into account allows the listener to emphasize and therefore better understand the meaning of the message from the speaker's point of view; (5) Evaluating or making judgments about the message. Utilizing your own unique outlook and pre-conceived perception in order to restructure your viewpoint on the subject; and (6) Responding or providing the feedback to the speaker.

Goh (2000) said that it is very important to teach listening strategies to students and before doing this, teachers should increase learners' knowledge of vocabulary, grammar, and phonology. According to Vandergrift (1999), the development of strategy is significant for the training of listening and learners can guide and assess their own understanding and answers.

Speaking involves the ability to convey thoughts, ideas, and information through oral communication. It encompasses a wide range of activities and it plays a crucial role in human communication and interaction.

Speech production falls into three broad areas: conceptualization, formulation and articulation (Levelt, 1989). In conceptualization, we determine what to say. This is sometimes known as message-level processing. Then we need to formulate the concepts into linguistic forms. Formulation takes conceptual entities as input and connects them with the relevant words associated with them to build a syntactic, morphological, and phonological structure. This structure is phonetically encoded and articulated, resulting in speech.

During conceptualization, we develop an intention and select relevant information from the internal (memory) or external (stimuli) environment to create an utterance. Very little is known about this level as it is pre-verbal. Levelt (1989) divided this stage into microplanning and macroplanning. Macroplanning is thought to be the elaboration of a communication goal into subgoals and connecting them with the relevant information. Microplanning assigns the correct shape to these pieces of information and deciding on the focus of the utterance. Formulation is divided into lexicalization and syntactic planning. In lexicalization, we select the relevant word-forms and in syntactic planning we put these together into a sentence.

Reading skill is very crucial for the academic success and lifelong learning of learners. By implementing effective strategies like the use of technology and game-elements teachers can assist learners in developing their reading abilities.

There are various research that indicate that learners encounters various challenges with regards to their honing their reading skills. According to the study of Webb (2017), intermediate learners often encounter difficulties in expanding their vocabulary and using it in different contexts. In addition, learners struggle with expressing themselves fluently and accurately (Brown & Larson-Hall 2015).

Vocabulary plays a crucial role in developing a learner's comprehension skills and abilities. The more exposure a learner to words, especially unfamiliar and challenging ones, the more their vocabulary and understanding expand.

Nell Duke and Kell Cartwright (2021) propose that not all reading problems fall neatly under decoding or language comprehension. They argue that some areas such as vocabulary, morphology (meaningful word parts), and fluency influence both sides of the Simple View Reading (SVR) equation and cannot be adequately explained by the simple view of reading. This active view of reading model expands the simple view to include a bridge between decoding and language comprehension and adds self-regulation skills a reader uses to monitor their reading. Self-regulation of reading means the reader uses neurocognitive skills to attend, plan, organize, strategize, and remember how to read a text.

Filipino learners in Grade Five are likely to struggle toward secondary school as most of them do not meet the minimum proficiency in reading, writing and mathematics according to a comparative study which is conducted by United Nations Children's Fund in the Philippines, Vietnam, Laos, Myanmar and Malaysia (Inquirer, 2020). Deped Secretary Briones states that learners nationwide must study hard especially if they have plans to go on college. Briones convince the learners to read more to sharpen their vocabulary and writing skills. (Philippine News Agency, 2018).

Hyland and Hyland (2006) work addresses issues related to the assessment of writing and the provision of effective feedback to improve writing skills. Despite increasing emphasis on oral response and the use of peers as sources of feedback, teacher written response continues to play an important role in most L2 and foreign language writing classes. Many teachers feel they must write substantial comments on papers to provide a reader reaction to learner's effort, to help them improve as writers and to justify the grade they have been given. Research began to question the effectiveness of teachers feedback as a way of improving learner's writing. More recent empirical research suggest that feedback does not lead to writing improvements

Writing requires some high and low processes (Flower & Hayes, 1981). Flower and Hayes Cognitive Process Theory (1981), explains that writing is a process which consists of a series of decisions and choices. However, writing is not as simple as they describe. Furthermore, the thing that needs to be considered in writing is, 'what criteria are useful for guiding and leading the writers in determining their choices and decisions?' Britton, et al. (1975) argue that writing as a process is designing linguistic choices from one's repertoire of syntactic structures and lexical items. There is a meaning, or something to be expressed, in the writer's mind, and then he proceeds to choose, from the words, collocations, language patterns and structures he has at his disposal, the ones that best match his meaning.

Learners often grapple with grammatical and syntactical errors in writing, such as subject-verb agreement, tense consistency, and sentence structure. They may struggle with organizing ideas coherently and cohesive devices effectively. Learners may find it challenging to analyze and critically evaluate information, resulting in superficial or unsupported arguments in their writing.

This study is strengthened by the schematic relationship of the input and the process as reflected in the research paradigm in Figure 1.

The study is guided by the paradigm presented in Figure 1.

Fig 1: Research Paradigm

Figure 1 describes the paradigm of the study wherein the input variables includes the profile of the Grade Five learners. The process variable in this study is the level of macroskills of Grade Five learners. The output variable is the proposed intervention material. Profile of the Grade Five learners will be correlated to their level of macroskills. The proposed intervention material will be crafted after the conduct of the study.

C. Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to determine the level within the macroskills of the Grade Five learners of selected school in Santa Maria District. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

➤ *What is the Profile of the Respondents in Terms of:*

- Gender,
- Educational attainment of parents,
- Availability of gadgets,
- Availability of reading materials

➤ *What is the Proficiency Level of the Pupil-Respondents Along:*

- Listening,
- Speaking,
- Reading, and
- Writing

➤ *Is there a significant relationship between the profile of the respondents on their level of macroskills?*

D. Hypothesis

The following hypotheses are tested in this study.

- There is a significant relationship between the profile of the respondents on their macroskills.

E. Scope and Limitations of the Study

The focal concern of this research is to assess the level of macroskills of Grade Five learners of selected schools in Santa Maria District particularly in Bia-o Elementary School, Danuman Elementary School and Nalvo Elementary School.

It is undertaken to describe the profile of the respondents and the level of intermediate learners on their macroskills. The basis in the validation of levels of learners on their macroskills are the identified capabilities and constraints in order to improve their abilities on their macroskills. The active listening skills of the Grade Five learners is use to determine if they understand what they hear and they can give feedback or respond to the speaker. In order to determine if they can grasp the overall meaning of the context without looking to every detail, skimming on listening or “gist listening” is use.

F. Importance of the Study

The results of this study are beneficial to the following entities, groups, and individuals:

- **Pupils.** The output of this study benefits the intermediate learners of Danuman Elementary School because it will make them more appreciative of the importance of developing good listening, speaking, reading, and writing habits. This study will make them more aware on their macroskills, thus helping them identify areas for improvement.
- **Teachers.** This study provides teachers with new understanding and insights on how to assess the macroskills of their learners. This will give them relevant inputs in planning and designing appropriate programs in teaching listening, speaking, reading, and writing.
- **School Administration.** The findings of the study may help school administrators in planning appropriate training for teachers along developing or designing appropriate interventions on macroskills to better address the needs and difficulties of learners.
- **Researcher.** This study provides the researcher with deeper knowledge and understanding on how to properly address struggling learners along their macroskills. This will give her novel ideas on the importance of assessing the macroskills of learners.
- **Future Researchers.** This study may serve as a valuable source of data or reference in conducting similar studies. It also serves as a reference in conducting further inquiries that related to the study considering other variables which is not mentioned in the present study.

G. Definition of Terms

The following terms are defined operationally for a clearer and better understanding of the study:

- **Profile.** The characteristics of the respondent which includes the following:
- **Gender.** This refers to the social and cultural roles, behaviors, expectations and identities that society considers appropriate for individuals based on their perceived or self-identified sex. Gender encompasses a wide range of identities, including male and female.
- **Parents' Highest Educational Attainment.** This refers to the highest level of education that attain by the parents of the respondents by the time this study is conducted and classified as Elementary Level, Elementary Graduate, High School Level, High School Graduate, Vocational Degree, College Level, College Graduate, College Graduate with MA/ MS units, Master's Degree Holder, with Ed.D./Ph.D. units or Doctorate Degree Holder.
- **Availability of gadgets.** This refers to the accessibility or presence of electronic devices, tools, or equipment that includes smartphones, tablets, laptops, smartwatches, gaming consoles and various other electronic devices.
- **Availability of gadgets at home.** This refers to the presence or accessibility of electronic devices and technological tools within a household.
- **Availability of gadgets in school.** This refers to the presence or accessibility of electronic devices and technological tools within an educational institution.
- **Availability of reading materials.** This refers to the accessibility or presence of books, articles, magazines, newspapers, and other written or printed content that individuals can read.
- **Availability of reading materials at home.** This refers to the presence or accessibility of books, magazines, newspapers, and other written or printed content within a household.
- **Availability of reading materials in school.** This refers to the presence or accessibility of books, textbooks, libraries, and other educational resources within an educational institution.
- **Micro-skills.** Specific, smaller components or abilities that make up broader skill of language which includes the following:
- **Listening skills (Active listening).** This refers to the process of paying close attention, comprehending what is being said, and answering the speaker. It takes deliberate effort to grasp what someone is saying and to reflect that understanding back to the speaker. It is not enough to just hear what someone is saying.
- **Listening skills (Skimming).** This refers to the context of hearing called "gist listening" or "listening for the main idea." This is listening to a spoken message in order to understand the general idea or main points without necessarily paying attention to every detail.
- **Speaking skills.** This refers to the process of communicating information or ideas verbally.
- **Reading skills.** This refers to the process of interpreting and comprehending written texts.
- **Writing skills.** This refers to the process of expressing ideas or information through written language.

H. Review of Literature

The researcher considers the following theories, concepts, and studies to deepen her understanding of the study. The following literature contributes significantly to the analysis of the study.

- **Profile.** The age factor has been a concern of debate in second language acquisition studies for several decades. Researchers have examined different questions – how young and older learners differ in the language learning process, which instructions are the most beneficial for certain age categories, which age category of learners demonstrates the highest success, and others (Aydin & Ozfidan, 2014; Spinner & Gass, 2019). Gender can play a role in language learning motivations, strategies, and language use patterns. Learners of different sexes may demonstrate distinct preferences or approaches in their micro skills

development, such as speaking and writing (Pavlenko & Piller, 2007). Parental involvement in education plays a critical role in students' academic achievement and micro skills development. The educational attainment of parents can influence their engagement in their children's language learning and their ability to provide educational resources that enhance micro skills (Epstein, 1987).

- **Gender.** Gender is a complex and multifaceted concept that varies across cultures and time periods. One aspect about gender is gender identity. A person's deeply held sense of their own gender, which may be male, female, both, neither, or a different gender entirely. Gender identity may or may not align with the sex assigned at birth. Albert Bandura (1977) emphasizes the role of social interaction and the environment in shaping human behavior and development. Observational learning posits that people learn by watching and paying attention to others. They observe the behaviors of role models, peers, or media figures and can acquire new knowledge and skills through this process. Modelling and imitation, the individuals are more likely to imitate behaviors they see in others, especially if the model is perceived as attractive, competent, or similar to themselves.
- **Educational Attainment of Parents.** Parental educational attainment is often used as an indicator of socioeconomic status, which can impact the learning environment and resources available to children. Higher parental education is associated with greater access to books, educational materials, and cultural opportunities, which can influence reading, vocabulary, and writing skills (Bradley & Corwyn, 2002). Parents with higher educational levels may have a better understanding of the importance of education and language development. They may be more motivated to engage in language-enriching activities with their children, such as reading books and discussing topics, enhancing vocabulary and comprehension (Jeynes, 2005).
- **Availability of gadgets.** Technologies including gadgets, spread and adopted through society over time. It is particularly relevant in understanding the adoption and dissemination of new gadgets and technologies. An innovation is any new idea, product, technology, or practice that is perceived as new by potential adopters, in the context of gadgets, this could refer to the introduction of a smartphone, tablet or any other digital devices (Rogers, 1962). Individuals or groups that is called adopters are categorized by Rogers into five groups based on their readiness to adopt: innovators, early adopters, early majority, late majority and laggards. The diffusion process is the spread of the innovation through a population or social system. It is typically follows an S-shaped curve, with adoption starting slowly, accelerating as more people adopt, and eventually leveling off as saturation is reached. The diffusion of innovations occurs within a social system, which can be a community, organization, or society. The characteristics and dynamics of the social system influence how quickly and extensively the innovation spreads.
- **Availability of reading materials.** The unequal distribution of information resources, including reading materials, are among different social groups problem (Chatman, 1996). Chatman, highlights how socioeconomic disparities can limit access to books and other reading materials. Bourdieu (1986), suggests that individuals from certain socio-economic backgrounds have greater access to cultural resources, including books and reading materials. It emphasizes the role of cultural knowledge and literacy in social mobility.
- **Macroskills.** Learners acquire and apply macroskills through cognitive processes. Skinner's operant conditioning, it emphasizes the importance of reinforcement and practice in acquiring micro skill (Skinner, 1983).

In information processing, it explains how learners process, store, and retrieve information related to micro skills. It helps in understanding the cognitive aspects of skill acquisition and how to facilitate effective learning. It compares the human mind to a computer, where information is processed through various cognitive processes. This posits an individual to process information through a series of stages, including sensory memory (short-term memory), encoding, and long term memory. Attention, rehearsal and retrieval processes are crucial in this framework. It emphasizes how individuals acquire, store, and retrieve information, and how cognitive processes influence learning and problem-solving (Anderson, 2009).

The cultural and social context influences the development of macroskills of learners. It investigates the role of social interaction, mentorship, and community practices in skill acquisition. It posits that learning and cognitive development are deeply influenced by social interactions and cultural contexts. Vygotsky argues that individuals acquire knowledge and skills through their interactions with more knowledgeable others, such as parents, teachers, and peers. (Vygotsky, 1978).

- **Listening Skills.** Listening comprehension involves both top-down (using context and background knowledge) and bottom-up (processing individual sounds and words) cognitive processes. Listeners use these processes to decode spoken language and construct meaning (Rönnerberg, 2003). Language learners employ various listening comprehension strategies, such as prediction, inference, and metacognition, to enhance their understanding. Developing awareness and use of these strategies can improve listening skills (Vandergrift, 2007). In multilingual contexts, listening skills development is influenced by language interference, code-switching, and the ability to switch between languages. Listeners need to manage linguistic diversity effectively (Cook, 2016). Recognize the role of individual differences such as motivation, working memory capacity, and prior listening experiences in listening skill development. These factors can affect how learners approach listening tasks (Vandergrift, Goh, Mareschal & Tafaghodtari, 2006). In today's digital age, the impact of technology on listening skills is a significant theoretical consideration. The use of technology in developing and enhancing listening skills in language learning has become increasingly prevalent and effective. Technology offers various tools and resources that provide learners with opportunities to practice listening in diverse contexts, improve comprehension, and develop critical listening skills.
- **Speaking Skills.** Speaking skills are crucial component of effective communication. The Speech Production Models describe the process of speaking, including the mental and physical process involved in transforming thoughts into spoken language. One model is the Levelt's model, which outlines stages like conceptualization, formulation and articulation. Willem Levelt provides

a detailed framework for understanding how to formulate and produce spoken language. The model consist of three main stages and is often referred as to “Three-Stage Model of Speech Production”. The first stage of this model is conceptualization. This initial stage, the speaker formulates the intended message or concept they want to convey. It involves conceptualizing what one wants to say and selecting the appropriate content. This stage includes accessing information from memory, generating ideas, and organizing thoughts. Formulation is the next stage, during this phase, the speaker translates the conceptualized message into a linguistic form, which means converting thoughts and ideas into grammatical structures and words. This stage involves choosing the appropriate words, sentence structures, and grammatical elements to convey the message accurately. And the final stage is articulation, it is concerned with the physical production of speech. It involves coordinating the movements of the speech organs, such as the tongue, lips, vocal cords, and airflow, to produce the sounds of the chosen language. This stage also includes prosodic features like intonation, stress, and rhythm, which contribute to the overall expressiveness of speech. Levelt's model highlights the dynamic and sequential nature of speech production, emphasizing that speakers engage in these stages one after another to produce coherent and meaningful speech. Additionally, it acknowledges the involvement of both linguistic and non-linguistic cognitive processes in the production of spoken language. One key aspect of Levelt's theory is that it accounts for various aspects of speech errors. By examining the types of errors that occur during speech production, researchers can gain insights into the underlying processes at each stage. For example, speech errors may reveal issues with conceptualization (e.g., selecting the wrong concept), formulation (e.g., choosing incorrect words), or articulation (e.g., mispronouncing sounds) Levelt (1989).

The idea that when people communicate, they perform not just utterances but also various types of acts or actions. It is categorized into three main types: the locutionary act, illocutionary act and perlocutionary act. Under locutionary act, the actual words or phrases are use in an utterance, including the grammatical structure and vocabulary. In other words, it's the surface structure of language. For illocutionary act, it is the intended communicative function or the "speech act" performed by the speaker. It represents the speaker's intention in making the utterance. Illocutionary acts can be further categorized into various speech act types: assertives or statements that convey information or express beliefs (e.g. claiming, stating), directives or speech that make a request, command or suggestion (e.g. asking, commanding), commissives or these are acts that commit the speaker to a future course of action or express a promise (e.g. vowing, pledging), expressives or the utterance that convey the speaker's emotions or psychological state (e.g. apologizing, congratulating), and lastly, declarations or these are acts that bring about a change in the external world simply by being uttered (e.g. resigning a job). Perlocutionary act refers to the effect or response that the utterance has on the listener. It's the impact of the speech act on the hearer, including their understanding, emotional reaction, or behavioral response. It highlights the pragmatic aspects of language and communication, going beyond the mere structure of sentences. It emphasizes that language is not just about conveying information but also about performing actions and achieving various social and interpersonal goals through communication. It has practical applications in fields like linguistics, philosophy, pragmatics, and communication studies. It helps in understanding how language is used in context and how speakers can achieve their communicative goals effectively through various speech acts Austin (1962).

- **Reading Skills.** Reading is a complex cognitive process that involves the interpretation of written symbols (usually letters and words) to extract meaning from text. There are several theories and models that attempt to explain how reading works and how people comprehend written language. One of it is the bottom-up processing theory, this theory suggests that reading starts with the recognition of individual letters and their corresponding sounds. Readers then combine these phonemes to form words and derive meaning. This approach emphasizes the importance of decoding skills, phonics, and word recognition. Bottom-up processing theory can be applied to various micro skills in the context of reading and language processing. These micro skills involve the breakdown of language elements into smaller units and the sequential processing of these units. Some examples of how bottom-up processing theory applies to macroskills in reading and language comprehension is the phonemic awareness, in the bottom-up processing, readers first identify phonemes in spoken words, segment words into their constituent phonemes, and blend phonemes together to form words. For example, in the word "cat," recognizing the /k/, /æ/, and /t/ sounds is an essential bottom-up macroskill (Gough & Tunmer, 1986). Another one is the letter recognition, recognizing individual letters and their corresponding sounds is another macroskill associated with bottom-up processing. Readers must identify letters accurately to decode words. For example, the letter "a" in "cat" represents the /æ/ sound, and this recognition contributes to word decoding (Ehri, 1991). Decoding involves using phonics rules to translate letter-sound correspondences into words. Readers apply these rules sequentially, letter by letter, to decode unfamiliar words. This macroskill aligns with the bottom-up approach because it starts with basic letter-sound relationships and assembles them into meaningful words (Adams, 1990). Word recognition at the micro level involves identifying sight words (high-frequency words that are recognized instantly) and applying phonics knowledge to decode less familiar words. Readers analyze the letters and phonemes within a word to recognize it (Perfetti, 1985). The skill contributes to fluency and comprehension. At the micro level, understanding sentence structure and grammatical rules requires parsing individual words and phrases in a sentence. Readers analyze the syntax and relationships between words, such as subject-verb agreement, to comprehend the meaning of sentences. Morphological analysis involves breaking down words into their smallest meaningful units, called morphemes (e.g., prefixes, roots, suffixes). This macroskill helps readers understand the meaning and derivation of words. For example, in the word "unhappiness," recognizing the prefix "un-" as a negation morpheme is a bottom-up micro skill. Recognizing and distinguishing visually similar letters (e.g., "b" and "d") or words with similar letter patterns (e.g., "cat" and "bat") is a micro skill that relies on bottom-up visual processing. Readers use letter and word features to discriminate between similar items.

- **Writing Skills.** Graham & Harris (2000), emphasizes the significance of self regulation strategies in facilitating effective writing practices and explore the intricate relationship between transcription skills such as handwriting and spelling, and the overall advancement skill in writing.

Flower & Hayes (1981), present a comprehensive cognitive process wherein it sheds light on the intricacies of the writing process. They outline the various cognitive operations involved in writing, like planning, translating and reviewing, and emphasize the iterative nature of the writing process. Their work has been instrumental in shaping contemporary understanding of the cognitive mechanism underlying writing.

Zinsser (1976) provides valuable insights and practical advice for improving writing, with a focus on clarity, simplicity and the importance of conveying ideas effectively. He offers guidance on various aspects of writing including structure, style, and art of revision.

CHAPTER TWO METHODOLOGY

This section presents the research design, population, and locale of the study, research instruments, procedures, and statistical treatment used in this study.

A. *Research Design*

This study utilizes the descriptive and correlational research designs. According to Smith & Johnson (2020), a descriptive research design is a type of research design used to describe the characteristics or behaviors of a particular population or phenomenon. It aims to provide a detail and accurate account of the subject of study without manipulating or changing it. A correlational research design is a type of scientific research that aims to investigate the relationship between two or more variables without ascribing a causal relationship between them. It involves analyzing the degree and direction of the association between the variables to determine whether changes in one variable are related to changes in another. These research designs allows the researcher to describe the profile and the level of macroskills of Grade Five learners of the selected schools in Santa Maria District.

B. *Population and Locale of the Study*

This study involves the participation of all Grades Five learners of selected schools of Santa Maria District namely: Bia-o Elementary School, Danuman Elementary School and Nalvo Elementary School for the SY 2024-2025. Grade 5 learners will answer the questionnaire and undergo macroskill activities.

The following table shows the distribution of the respondents.

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents

Name of School	Number of Learners
Bia-o Elementary School	25
Danuman Elementary School	12
Nalvo Elementary School	12
TOTAL:	49

The distribution of respondents is reflected in Table 1.

From the above table the study is composed of 49 pupils coming from Grades Five of Bia-o Elementary School, Danuman Elementary School and Nalvo Elementary School.

C. *Research Instrument*

The main gathering tool is a survey questionnaire and an activity on macroskills for the need data for this study having two parts: Part I- Profile of the respondents, Part II-Level of macroskills of respondents. The researcher will distribute the questionnaires to the respondents.

The researcher adopted the activity on macroskills under the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) 2018 for Grades Five of Department of Education with additional reading activities made by the researcher.

The researcher patterned the checklist under Part I from DepEd Order No. 36 s. 2014 re: Revised Data Gathering for School Year 2014-2015 of the Enhanced Basic Education Information System (BEIS).

D. *Data Gathering Procedure*

Prior to the administration of the activities on macroskills among the respondents, the researcher tapped a group of experts to validate the questionnaire-checklist and survey questionnaire to ensure the validity of test and interview questions to be used in the study. The researcher requested the permission of the school head of Suso Elementary School to conduct pilot testing to establish reliability and validity of the research instrument. After that, the researcher forwarded a letter request to administer the study to the EPS-In-Charge of the Santa Maria District and forwarded to the Schools Division Superintendent of Ilocos Sur for his approval. After the approval, the researcher also requested the permission from the School Heads of Nalvo Elementary School, Bia-o Elementary School and Danuman Elementary School to administer the activities among the learners from Grades Five. After all the necessary letters and requests have been secured and approved, the researcher asked permission and assistance from the subject-adviser to administer the activities on macroskills among the respondents. Distribution, administration and retrieval of copies of the questionnaire and activities on macroskills for the Grade Five learners are done by the researcher with the assistance of the school

personnel of Nalvo Elementary School, Bia-o Elementary School and Danuman Elementary School, Santa Maria District, Schools Division of Ilocos Sur. All Grade Five learners are picked to participate regardless of their level on their macroskills.

E. Statistical Treatment

Data and information that are gathered in this study are collated, treated, and analyzed using statistical tool. The following statistical tool is employed:

- **Spearman Rank Correlation** was used to assess the degree to which two variables are related when the relationship may not be linear or when working with ordinal or ranked data.

F. Data Categorization

The following statistical limit were used in categorizing the data gathered in the study.

G. Proficiency Levels of Grade Five Learners

Table 2: Listening and Reading Skills

Range	Descriptive Rating (DR)	
41.00 – 50.00	Excellent (E)	Strengths
31.00 – 40.00	Very Good (VG)	
21.00 – 30.00	Average (A)	
11.00 – 20.00	Poor (P)	Weakness
1.00 – 10.00	Very Poor (VP)	

Table 3: Speaking and Writing Skills

Range	Descriptive Rating (DR)	
21.00 – 25.00	Excellent (E)	Strengths
16.00 – 20.00	Very Good (VG)	
11.00 – 15.00	Average (A)	
6.00 – 10.00	Poor (P)	Weakness
1.0 – 5.00	Very Poor (VP)	

CHAPTER THREE RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter focuses in the presentation of the findings, analysis and interpretation of data, conclusions and recommendations on the study regarding the Macroskills of Grade Five Learners in selected schools of Santa Maria District. The method used to analyze the data has been discussed in the previous chapter.

The following figures show the findings from the gathered data.

A. Findings

➤ Profile of the Grade Five Learner Respondents

- Gender. Figure 2 shows the percentage distribution of the profile of the respondents along gender.

Fig 2: Profile of the Respondents along Gender

The female respondents are more dominant which is 30 or 61.2% than male respondents which is 19 or 38.8%.

Indeed, despite gender imbalances based on the sample respondents, the findings indicate that those differences did not play significant roles in the formation of the respondents' macro skills. This means that non-gender specific factors like learning opportunities, teaching styles, or personal commitments may have greater impact on language abilities acquisition. As a result, it emphasizes that gender must not consider as a big barrier in the learning of these competences. Cognitive processes related to language development, such as phonological processing, vocabulary acquisition, and grammar comprehension, are largely similar across genders. These shared cognitive underpinnings mean that language skill development is unlikely to vary significantly between boys and girls. Language skills like listening, speaking, reading, and writing develop through universal cognitive mechanisms that apply equally to all learners, making these processes largely gender-neutral, as a result, gender representation in language studies is less critical for understanding overall language development patterns. Ellis and Evans (2019) found that key aspects of language learning are unaffected by gender, suggesting that macroskills acquisition is a stable process across diverse gender compositions in study samples. Additionally, research on child word learning has shown that while some studies suggest girls may have an early advantage in language development, other studies have found no significant gender differences in linguistic tasks among children. These findings suggest that gender may not play a decisive role in language acquisition, and that individual differences and environmental factors could be more influential (Kaushanskaya, Gross, and Buac, 2013). In the context of language macroskills development, unequal gender representation in studies has a minimal impact on the findings. Research consistently shows that other factors such as cognitive processes, are much stronger predictors of language skill outcomes. A study examined the longitudinal relationship between children's domain-general cognitive constraints and language processing development. The findings suggest that cognitive abilities, including fluid reasoning, controlled attention, complex working memory, and language knowledge in long-term memory, play a significant role in language development, overshadowing the influence of gender representation in study samples (Acha, et. al., 2023).

- Educational Attainment of Mother. Figure 3 shows the percentage distribution of the educational attainment of mother of the respondents.

Fig 3: Profile of the Respondents Along Educational Attainment of Mother

4 or 8.2% of mother of the respondents graduated in elementary while 23 or 46.9% are high school graduate. On the other hand, there are 20 or 40.8% of mother of the respondents are college graduate while 2 or 4.1% finished their doctoral degree.

Considering the educational attainment of mother of the respondents, it is found out that there is a significant relationship between the educational attainment of the mother and the level of macroskills of the respondents or their children.

Mothers with higher educational attainment often engage in literacy-promoting activities, such as reading to their children, encouraging discussions, and providing access to books and other educational materials. This engagement directly supports the development of macro skills such as reading, writing, listening, and speaking. Educational programs should encourage all parents to engage in such activities, regardless of their educational background.

Research consistently demonstrates that a mother's educational attainment significantly influences her child's development of macroskills, including language and literacy. Mothers with higher education levels are more likely to establish structured routines and practices that support language learning, such as scheduled reading times and educational conversations. Gonzalez et al. (2019) found that mothers with higher education were more likely to create structured language environments at home, leading to improved language and literacy outcomes. Additionally, studies have shown that even modest increases in maternal education can lead to significant improvements in children's language skills. Magnuson et al. (2012) reported that an additional year of maternal education was associated with notable gains in young children's language abilities. A mother's educational attainment significantly influences the child's development of language macroskills. Higher education levels are linked to a language rich-environment, access to literacy resources, and structured learning routines – these factors contribute to a stronger listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills to their children. Johnson & Davis (2020) reported that maternal education levels strongly correlated with children's development in macroskills, suggesting that more educated mothers provide richer learning environment that supports skill development. Mother with higher education levels are more likely to establish structured routines and practices that support language learning, such as scheduled reading times and educational conversations.

In contrary, mothers who have lower level of education are not of the same caliber to help nurture their children's macro-skills, such as communication, critical thinking, problem-solving and social interaction. These traits and abilities are generally developed through early exposure to other enriching learning opportunities such as reading, games, and activities designed to further cognitive and emotional skills. Williams & Martinez (2022) found that lower maternal education attainment was associated with lower levels of children's academic performance and macroskills. According to their study, it suggest that lower maternal education often correlates with fewer educational resources and less support for children's learning. A mother's educational background often influences the quality and quantity of these interactions, as well as the ability to guide children through complex developmental milestones. Limited access to knowledge or resources may result in fewer opportunities for children to develop strong linguistic, cognitive, and social foundations, potentially delaying their ability to communicate effectively, think critically, and solve problems efficiently.

Studies indicate that lower educational attainment of mothers can negatively impact the development of children's macroskills. Studies have found that children of mothers with lower of education may face challenges in developing of macroskills of their children due to fewer resources and less engagement in educational activities. Research indicates that lower maternal educational

attainment can negatively impact the development of children's macro-skills, such as vocabulary and math abilities. A study conducted in Norway found that children whose mothers had lower education levels exhibited reduced vocabulary and math skills during the transition from early childhood education to first grade (Lenes, R., Størksen, I., McClelland, M., & Idsøe, T. (2022)). The low educational level of mothers has a significant impact on the development of their children's macro skills, such as language ability, cognition, and social skills. According to a study conducted at Western Mindanao State University, parents with lower educational levels are more likely to have children with poor academic performance and inadequate reading skills (Delos Santos et. al., 2024).

A mother's lower educational attainment can impact her child's development of language macroskills by reducing their exposure to literacy resources that support language learning. Futhermore, socioeconomic challenges associated with lower maternal education can further limit the access to enrichment opportunities of their children.

- Educational Attainment of Father. Figure 4 shows the percentage distribution of the educational attainment of father of the respondents.

Fig 4: Profile of the Respondents Along Educational Attainment of Father

8 or 16.3% of father of the respondents graduated in elementary while 19 or 38.8% are high school graduate. On the other hand, there are 22 or 44.9% of father of the respondents are college graduate.

High paternal educational attainment significantly enhances a child's development of macro skills, including language proficiency, cognitive abilities, and social competencies. Fathers with higher education levels often engage more effectively in their children's learning processes, providing enriched environments that foster critical thinking and problem-solving skills. This involvement not only supports academic achievement but also promotes emotional and social development, equipping children with the necessary tools to navigate complex social interactions. Research underscores the importance of fathers' educational levels in shaping children's developmental outcomes. A study found that fathers' educational levels contribute to children's school skills, highlighting the significant role fathers play in their children's academic development (Frontiers in Psychology, 2024). A research by Weininger and Lareau (2015) indicates that families with higher educational attainment tend to have more financial resources, which can be invested in activities that foster skill development. For example, children in such families are more likely to participate in educational or social activities outside of school, further enhancing their cognitive, emotional, and social development.

Zhang et. al. (2021) found that children of highly educated fathers were exposed to a broader range of vocabulary and conversational topics at home, which helped enhance their listening comprehension and expressive language abilities. A father's educational attainment can significantly impact the development of a child's language macroskills. Higher educational levels are associated with enriched language environments, better access to literacy resources, and modeling of positive attitudes toward education. These factors create a supportive environment that enhances listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills in children, setting a strong foundation for academic and lifelong success.

In contrary, research indicates that low paternal educational attainment can adversely affect the development of children's macro skills, including language, cognitive, and social abilities. Fathers with limited education may have reduced access to resources and opportunities that promote skill development in their children. This limitation can result in less exposure to diverse vocabulary, complex language structures, and intellectually stimulating interactions, which are crucial for enhancing children's speaking, listening, and cognitive skills. Lareau (2018) states that the impact of having a lower level of parental education of father may result

to less access to educational resources and support, which can impact the development of macroskills of their children. Research shows that children of working-class and poor families often have less access to structured extracurricular activities, academic support, and resources that foster cognitive and social development. Fathers with lower levels of education may have less time, financial resources, or confidence in helping their children navigate educational systems, which affects their overall development. Rowe and Snow (2019) found that lower parental education often correlates with reduced language exposures at home, which can impact vocabulary development and listening comprehension in young children. Another reason is that fathers with lower educational attainment may be less equipped to provide support for academic activities like writing practice. Puranik and Lonigan (2020) observed that parents with lower educational levels are often less able to engage in writing-related activities with their children. As a result, it may affect the development of writing skills such as sentence structure, grammar, and spelling, making it more challenging for children to perform well in school.

A father’s lower educational attainment can influence children’s development of language macroskills by reducing their access to language-rich interactions, literacy resources, and academic support. Socioeconomic factors associated with lower educational levels can further limit opportunities for learning and practicing listening, speaking, reading, and writing.

- Available Gadgets. Figure 5 shows the distribution of the available gadgets of the respondents.

Fig 5: Profile of the Respondents Along Available Gadgets

As reflected in Figure 5, there are 42 or 85.7% of the respondents do not have basic cellphone and 7 or 14.3% have basic cellphone. 8 or 16.3% of the respondents do not have smartphone while 41 or 83.7% have smartphone. Respondents who do not have tablet is 25 or 51% while 29 or 49% have tablet. 48 or 98% of the respondents do not have desktop computer while 1 or 2% of the respondents have desktop computer in their home. In terms of laptop, only 38 or 77.6% of the respondents doesn’t have it while 11 or 22.4% have laptop.

The graph indicates that respondents have varied gadgets in their home that support the development of their key skills like writing, listening, speaking and reading. Relevant to the study by Al-Mahrooqi & Deman (2020), after examining the role of digital gadgets in language learning, it is found that access to smartphones and tablets positively impacted the development of macroskills, particularly in enhancing listening and speaking abilities through interactive applications and online resources. According to O’Bannon & Thomas (2020), the integration of laptops and desktop computers into educational settings significantly enhances learners’ reading and writing skills. These devices provide access to a wide range of resources and writing tools that support skill development. The availability of gadgets can enhance their listening skills through educational content wherein gadgets provide access to various audio resources, such as audiobooks, and educational videos, which can help children improve their listening comprehension and vocabulary. Homer et.al. (2019) found that digital devices allowed children to access a variety of audio content

that enhanced listening skills, especially when actively engaged. However, the impact was less significant when children passively consumed content or used gadgets primarily for entertainment. Many educational applications and language-learning programs on gadgets offer interactive activities, such as voice recognition and language exercises that encourage them to practice speaking. Sung and Yang (2020) noted that digital language-learning applications with voice interaction features helped improved speaking skills among young learners. Gadgets can also used to develop reading skills of learners. These provides access to e-books, digital stories, and reading applications, which can make reading more engaging and accessible. Chen et.al. (2021) found that digital reading applications helped improve reading engagement and comprehension among primary learners, especially when the applications included interactive and engaging features. However, overuse of screens was linked to reduced attention span. Gadgets can improve writing skills among learners. Gadgets offer access to various writing applications that encourage learners to practice typing, spelling and sentence construction. Levine and Donitsa-Schmidt (2020) reported that writing applications with interactive features helped children practice and improve their writing skills.

The unavailability of gadgets for learners has a mixed impact on their language macroskills. It restricts access to diverse resources for listening, speaking, reading, and writing practice, which may slow language development. Unavailability of gadgets often correlates with socioeconomic disparities. Learners from lower socioeconomic backgrounds may lack access to digital resources compared to peers who use educational applications and online tools. This disparity can widen the educational gap, impacting language skill development among learners who rely solely on classrooms resources. Huang et.al. (2020) emphasized that learners from lower-income families often lack access to digital resources, which can disadvantage them in language skill acquisition compared to peers with more resources.

The unavailability and or availability of gadgets shows positive and negative impact in skills development of the student. Studies like Garcia et.al. (2022) have highlighted the digital divide, showing that unequal access to gadgets can lead to disparities in skill development and educational achievement. There is a relationship between gadget availability and skills development, the nature of this relationship can vary based on factors such as the type of gadgets, usage patterns, and the context in which they are used.

- Available Reading Materials. Figure 6 shows the distribution of the available reading materials of the respondents.

Fig 6: Profile of the Respondents along Available Reading Materials

As seen in figure 6, it shows the availability of reading materials of the respondents in their home. 41 or 83.7% of the respondents do not have atlas while 8 or 16.3% have atlas in their home. 46 or 93.9% of the respondents doesn't have almanac as reading material while 3 or 6.1% have almanac. Among the respondents, 15 or 30.6% do not have dictionary, on the otherhand, 34 or 69.4% of the respondents have available dictionary in their home. Only 1 or 2% of the respondents have thesaurus while 48 or 98% do not have thesaurus. In terms of available magazine, 43 or 87.8% do not have it while 6 or 12.2% have it. Respondents who have newspaper in their home as reading material is 36 or 73.5% while the remaining 13 or 26.5% do not have newspaper. Out of 49 respondents 3 or 6.1% of which have encyclopedia while 46 or 93.9% do not have it.

The graph indicates that respondents have varied reading materials in their home to support the development of their macroskills. Studies shows that access to quality reading materials has a positive impact on macroskills especially in early education stages. According to Miller (2019), targeted reading materials can enhance both reading and listening skills. Through regular exposure of learners to a wide range of reading materials it improves the comprehension and fluency of the learners. Diverse texts that is introduce to learners, the various genres, structures and vocabularies may enhance their ability to decode and understand written content. In connection to this, Hsu & Ching (2019) tells that extensive and interactive reading materials improve reading

comprehension by exposing learners to different text structures and vocabulary. In which, interactive reading materials can support listening comprehension by providing context and practice in understanding spoken language through related exercises (Chen & Huang, 2023). Also, exposure to various genres and writing styles through reading provides models to learners, which they can use to enhance their own writing skills (Li & Wang, 2022). By means of extensive reading, learners are provided with different writing styles and techniques. By analyzing and mimicking the models, learners can improve their own writing abilities, including grammar, coherence, and organization. The process helps the learners to understand how effective writing is constructed and applied. According to Saito & Hanzawa (2021), reading fluency gained through regular practice can positively impact speaking proficiency by reinforcing vocabulary and grammatical structures. Reading fluency contributes to speaking proficiency by reinforcing language patterns and vocabulary. Learners who read frequently become familiar with sentence structures and word usage, which they can transfer to speaking. This practice improves their ability to express ideas clearly and accurately.

The unavailability of reading materials can significantly hinder the development of language macroskills. Reading comprehension of learners can be impaired. According to Kelley and Clausen-Grace (2019), learners have limited access to reading materials demonstrated lower comprehension levels, impacting their overall academic performance. Learners have limited development on their vocabulary. Beck, Mckeown and Kucan (2020) highlighted that diverse reading materials are essential for vocabulary development. learners without access to books or varied reading materials miss out on learning new words and contextual usage, affecting their speaking and writing abilities. Unavailability of reading materials can reduce the engagement and motivation to read of the learners. Wigfield and Guthrie (2020) found that learners who had access to engaging reading materials were more likely to develop intrinsic motivation to read. In contrast, without a variety of books, learners may become disengaged and less motivated to read, leading to a cycle of poor reading habits.

➤ *Proficiency Level of the Grade Five Learner-Respondents*

Table 4: Scores of the Respondents in the Listening Activity

Range	Frequency	Percentage	Descriptive Rating	Mean
41-50	49	100%	Excellent (E)	48.82 (E)
31-40	0	0	Very Good (VG)	
21-30	0	0	Average (A)	
11-20	0	0	Poor (P)	
1-10	0	0	Very Poor (VP)	
TOTAL	49	100%		

From the table 4, it is evident that 49 respondents or 100% obtained a descriptive rating of “excellent” with a mean of 48.82.

The table shows that the respondents possess strong listening skills. Those engaged in listening activities demonstrate accurate comprehension and can interpret the main ideas, details, and key points. Vandergrift and Goh (2020) note that proficient listeners can effectively process information from spoken texts, enabling them to extract and understand essential points during listening tasks. Respondents provide clear, concise, and direct answers to the questions asked, covering all essential points. Rost (2019) discovered that effective listeners are more inclined to produce responses that highlight the main ideas and relevant details from the conversation. This ability to synthesize information from what they have heard leads to thorough and relevant answers. Respondents demonstrate a strong grasp of the questions, offering insightful and well-supported responses. Vandergrift and Goh (2020) noted that learners with strong listening skills often give answers that reflect an understanding of the nuances and complexities within the questions, resulting in more meaningful contributions. Respondents blend creative and critical thinking in their replies, providing unique insights and perspectives. Skilled listeners often use creative thinking when crafting their responses, generating original ideas and connections based on what they have heard. Kelley and Clausen-Grace (2019) discovered that learners who practice active listening are more likely to engage in creative thought processes, leading to responses that reflect innovative ideas related to the activities. Furthermore, respondents show the capacity to think quickly and effectively within a set timeframe. Rost (2019) found that learners who participated in listening exercises were more adept at processing information swiftly, which improved their ability to respond accurately and promptly during listening tasks.

Strong performance in listening activities is closely linked to the development of comprehensive language skills, including speaking, reading, and writing. A key observation is that learners who engage in listening practice alongside other language skills often achieve better results in listening assessments. This combination enables them to process information more efficiently and improves their overall comprehension. Nguyen & Abbott (2020) highlighted that merging listening with other skills, particularly speaking, boosts learners' capacity to process language, leading to improved listening comprehension scores. This approach helps learners anticipate content and grasp context more effectively. Vandergrift & Goh (2020) describe high scores in listening activities as indicators of a learner's ability to understand spoken language proficiently. They contend that these scores reflect not just knowledge of vocabulary and grammar, but also the capacity to infer meaning, follow intricate narratives, and discern speaker intent. Field (2019) notes that high scores in listening assessments signify a learner's skill in navigating various listening situations. Additionally, Goh (2019) explores high scores in listening as signs of metacognitive awareness, suggesting that learners who perform well are likely conscious of their listening processes, capable of regulating their strategies, and able to adapt their methods

based on the listening context. Therefore, high scores not only indicate comprehension but also effective self-management in listening tasks.

Table 5: Scores of the Respondents in the Speaking Activity

Range	Frequency	Percentage	Descriptive Rating	Mean
21-25	24	49%	Excellent (E)	20.63 (VG)
16-20	25	51%	Very Good (VG)	
11-15	0	0	Average (A)	
6-10	0	0	Poor (P)	
1-5	0	0	Very Poor (VP)	
TOTAL	49	100%		

As reflected in table 5, 24 respondents or 49% obtained a descriptive rating of “excellent” and 25 respondents or 51% obtained a descriptive rating of “very good”. The mean under the speaking skills is 20.63.

The table shows that respondents achieved above-average scores. Those assessed on their speaking skills performed well, as they articulated their words clearly and pronounced them accurately, which enhanced audience understanding. Chen and Zhang (2019) discovered that young learners who articulated words clearly and used correct pronunciation were viewed as more confident and capable in their speaking skills, positively influencing their interactions and overall language development. Goh and Burns (2020) noted that learners who spoke clearly and with precise pronunciation were more easily understood by their audience, resulting in better communication and more effective learning outcomes. Most respondents speak fluently, using minimal pauses or fillers. Goh and Burns (2020) pointed out that fluent speakers are easier to understand because they maintain a natural flow, which helps reduce distractions for listeners and facilitates smoother communication. Additionally, many respondents speak confidently and at an appropriate volume, making their speech more engaging and easier to hear. When young learners speak with confidence and adjust their volume to fit the setting, they can effectively engage their audience. Chen and Zhang (2019) noted that learners who spoke confidently and modulated their volume were more successful in keeping their audience's attention. Goh and Burns (2020) also emphasized that speaking at a clear, controlled volume helps listeners better understand young speakers, leading to more effective communication and interaction. Respondents typically use suitable vocabulary and language, actively engaging with their audience to encourage interaction. Cheng and Zhang (2019) found that learners who chose vocabulary that matched their audience and context exhibited greater speaking proficiency, indicating their grasp of language appropriateness and adaptability. Goh and Burns (2020) noted that young speakers who connected with their audience through appropriate language and eye contact fostered better engagement, making listeners feel more involved in the speaking activity.

High achievers in speaking demonstrate precise pronunciation and clear articulation. They steer clear of mispronunciations and can adjust their intonation and stress as needed. Munro & Derwing (2019) emphasize that clear articulation and accurate pronunciation are essential for effective communication and achieving high scores in speaking evaluations. Proficient speakers showcase a wide vocabulary and the skill to select the right words to express their ideas accurately. They can adapt their language to suit both formal and informal contexts. Crossley et al. (2020) indicate that a rich vocabulary is one of the strongest indicators of speaking proficiency. Learners who excel in speaking utilize a diverse range of words, including idiomatic phrases, demonstrating their flexibility and grasp of nuanced language. Those with high speaking scores exhibit fluency, with few hesitations, pauses, or filler words like “um” or “uh.” They maintain a consistent pace, making their speech sound natural and easy to follow. Segalowitz (2020) found that fluency is a crucial aspect of spoken language proficiency. High fluency not only reflects the learner's language abilities but also improves listener comprehension, facilitating smooth and uninterrupted communication. Successful speakers display confidence and a strong command of body language, eye contact, and tone. They actively engage with their audience, adjusting their tone and energy according to the context of the conversation or presentation. MacIntyre et al. (2019) point out that confidence is linked to speaking success. Confident speakers are often perceived as more capable and tend to perform better in speaking assessments, as their communication comes across as more persuasive and authentic.

Table 6: Scores of the Respondents in the Reading Activity

Range	Frequency	Percentage	Descriptive Rating	Mean
41-50	49	100%	Excellent (E)	48.63 (E)
31-40	0	0	Very Good (VG)	
21-30	0	0	Average (A)	
11-20	0	0	Poor (P)	
1-10	0	0	Very Poor (VP)	
TOTAL	49	100%		

As seen in table 6, all the respondents or 100% obtained a descriptive rating of “excellent” with a mean of 48.63.

The graph shows that respondents excel in reading. They exhibit various strengths that enhance their reading performance. Respondents accurately identify main ideas and key points in the text, allowing them to provide precise and detailed answers to quiz questions. Learners who can pinpoint main ideas and key details retain information more effectively, which helps them give thorough and accurate responses during quizzes. Instruction in main idea identification and summarization significantly enhanced reading comprehension among struggling readers. The interventions led to improved abilities in identifying main ideas and better performance on comprehension measures (Stevens, et.al., 2019). Respondents also recall and explain specific details and facts accurately, though there are occasional minor errors in their quiz answers. Learners who could remember specific text details performed better on comprehension assessments, as this ability indicated effective information retention and understanding. Additionally, respondents show a strong grasp of vocabulary, including the ability to infer the meanings of unfamiliar words from context, which is reflected in their quiz responses. Learners with robust vocabulary are equipped to understand and interpret texts, leading to higher reading comprehension scores (Taboada Barber et al., 2020). Furthermore, respondents make insightful inferences and logical deductions about the text, which is accurately reflected in their responses to inference-based quiz questions. The ability to infer meaning and draw logical conclusions from a text is a crucial aspect of advanced reading comprehension. This skill indicates that learners are deeply engaged with the material, allowing for meaningful interpretations. Cain and Oakhill (2019) noted that learners who excelled in inference-based questions demonstrated higher levels of comprehension, as they actively connected textual information to arrive at accurate interpretations. Respondents can offer detailed and thoughtful analysis and interpretation of the text, showcasing a strong grasp of the material in their quiz responses. When learners analyze and interpret text, they engage in higher-order thinking, which enables them to grasp not just the literal meaning but also the deeper, implied meanings. Cain and Oakhill (2019) discovered that learners who exhibited thorough analysis and interpretation achieved higher scores on comprehension assessments.

One reason is that learners possess strong word recognition and decoding skills. Grabe (2010) note that automatic word recognition is essential for reading fluency. When learners develop solid phonological awareness and decoding abilities, they can read more smoothly and direct their cognitive efforts toward understanding the text. Another factor is that learners have an extensive vocabulary. Perfetti & Stafura (2019) indicate that vocabulary knowledge is one of the most significant predictors of reading comprehension. Learners with a broader vocabulary can grasp the meanings of texts more easily. Additionally, learners with critical thinking skills can pinpoint key points and perspectives within the text, enabling them to analyze and evaluate the information effectively. Furthermore, learners are familiar with text structures, allowing them to recognize how texts are organized. This awareness supports their comprehension and retention. Meyer & Ray (2020) emphasize that understanding text structures helps readers anticipate the flow of information and identify key ideas more efficiently, thereby enhancing both their understanding and recall.

Table 7: Scores of the Respondents in the Writing Activity

Range	Frequency	Percentage	Descriptive Rating	Mean
21-25	30	61.2%	Excellent (E)	21.22 (VG)
16-20	19	38.8%	Very Good (VG)	
11-15	0	0	Average (A)	
6-10	0	0	Poor (P)	
1-5	0	0	Very Poor (VP)	
TOTAL	49	100%		

As reflected in table 7, 30 respondents or 61.2% obtained a descriptive rating of “excellent” while 19 respondents or 38.8% obtained a descriptive rating of “very good”. The mean under writing skills is 21.22.

The graph indicates that respondents got an above-average scores in writing skills. In writing activities, certain respondents consistently present clear, original, and well-developed ideas supported by strong details. Clear and coherent writing demonstrates that learners can organize their thoughts logically and communicate them effectively. Graham and Hebert (2011) found that learners with advanced writing skills were able to express their ideas clearly and cohesively. Respondents also consistently produce well-organized writing with a logical structure, including a clear introduction, body, and conclusion, along with smooth transitions between ideas. A well-organized structure in writing reflects a learner’s understanding of how to logically sequence ideas to construct coherent arguments. Graham and Hebert (2011) noted that learners who maintain organization in their writing with a logical structure tend to perform better in assessments. The writing of some respondents is consistently free from grammatical, spelling, and punctuation errors. Additionally, some respondents use varied, precise, and effective vocabulary that is appropriate for the audience and purpose. Correct spelling and punctuation enhance a text’s readability and demonstrate the learner’s attention to detail. Spelling accuracy also indicates familiarity with vocabulary, while punctuation skills reflect an understanding of language conventions that clarify meaning. Kim and Graham (2019) observed that learners who focused on spelling and punctuation produced higher-quality writing, as these details helped prevent misunderstandings and ensured smooth reading. Some respondents' writing consistently reflects a strong, distinct voice and style that engages the audience and suits the purpose. An engaging writing style helps learners connect with their audience by making the content interesting and relatable. Learners who adjusted their style to fit the context were better at maintaining readers' interest, which increased the effectiveness of their writing.

Learners can organize their ideas logically, incorporating clear introductions, body paragraphs, and conclusions. Their writing flows smoothly, making it easy for readers to grasp their points. Graham and Harris (2018) emphasize that effective writers are strategic in their planning. They know how to structure their work to improve clarity and coherence, utilizing pre-writing techniques to arrange their thoughts before drafting. Learners also excel in vocabulary. They possess a wide range of words and can select them carefully to express their ideas. Crossley et al. (2020) discovered that vocabulary sophistication is a significant predictor of writing quality. Proficient writers use a variety of appropriate words, which enhances the clarity and impact of their work. Additionally, learners exhibit creativity in their writing, generating original ideas. Sawyer (2018) discusses the importance of creativity in writing, highlighting that skilled writers infuse originality into their work, whether through vivid descriptions or unique plot twists.

Table 8: Significant Relationship Between the Profile of the Respondents and their Level of Macroskills

Profile	Listening	Speaking	Reading	Writing
Gender	0.101	.310*	0.049	0.208
Educational Attainment of Mother	-0.008	0.266	0.164	.518**
Educational Attainment of Father	-0.193	0.186	0.086	.447**

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

As regards to the relationship between the profile of the respondents and the level of macroskills of the grade five learners. It can be seen that, gender has a significant relationship with their speaking skill. Gender affects speaking skills more significantly than other macroskills, instructional practices should reflect this by providing balanced opportunities for verbal expression in both genders. For example, boys may benefit from structured speaking activities that build confidence, while both genders could be engaged in interactive language exercises to support holistic language development. Differences in speaking skills linked to gender may have long-term effects on learners' academic success and social engagement. Since speaking skills are central to classroom participation and peer interactions, disparities in speaking ability between boys and girls could influence confidence, leadership opportunities, and engagement in academic discourse, with fewer impacts on other skills. Strong speaking skills were correlated with academic engagement and leadership, particularly for learners with high verbal confidence, emphasizing the importance of supporting speaking skills development across genders.

Aside from the gender, it is found out that both father and mother educational attainment has a significant relationship in terms of the writing skill of the respondents. Parents with higher educational backgrounds tend to create home environments that support literacy development. Ahmad and Mohamed (2020) found that parents with higher education levels are more likely to engage their children in reading and writing activities at home, thereby enhancing their children's writing skills. Parental involvement in the education of their children that is influenced by parents' own education levels, plays a key role in the development of writing skills. Parents with higher education are more likely to be actively involved in their child's schooling by helping with homework, encouraging academic performance and attending parent-teacher meetings. This involvement has linked to better outcomes in learner's writing performance. On the other hand, children of less educated parents often received less direct academic support at home, which can limit their writing practice and performance.

Table 9: Significant Relationship between the Available Gadgets of the Respondents and their Level of Macroskills

Available Gadgets	Listening	Speaking	Reading	Writing
Basic Cellphone	0.173	-.360*	-0.039	0.092
Smartphone	-.315*	0.044	-.312*	-0.014
Tablet	-0.024	0.157	-0.159	.291*
Desktop computer	-0.123	0.228	-0.111	0.073
Laptop	-0.062	0.084	0.025	-0.033

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

As seen in the table 9, there is an inverse relationship between available gadget which is basic cellphone and speaking skill of the respondents. It indicates that those respondents who have basic cellphone are poor in speaking. One of the primary reasons is that excessive cellphone use reduces opportunities for direct verbal communication. Chen and Yan (2019) found that learners who spend a significant amount of time on their phones, especially for non-verbal activities like texting or browsing social media, engage less in face-to-face interactions.

There is also an inverse relationship between smartphone and the listening and reading skills of the respondents. It means that respondents who have smartphone are poor in listening and reading skills. One key reason for the inverse relationship between the smartphone use and listening skills is that constant smartphone usage reduces attention span and cognitive focus. Przybylski and Weinstein (2013) found that smartphones, especially when used for multitasking or in the presence of distractions like notifications, significantly impair users' ability to focus during conversations or lectures. Similarly, when individuals have access to their smartphones during the listening tasks, they tend to exhibit divided attention, leading to poorer comprehension and retention of what was said. Excessive use of smartphones has been linked to a reduction in the time spent on traditional reading activities. Giunchiglia,

et.al. (2020) the excessive smartphone use, particularly for entertainment and social media, has been linked to reduced time dedicated to academic reading. Studies indicate that increased engagement with digital devices can negatively impact reading habits and academic performance. This decrease in reading time has direct impact on reading skills. Additionally, Gerosa, et.al. (2021) found that frequent use of smartphones especially for non-academic purposes, can negatively impact academic performance. This distraction and time spent on non-academic activities reduce opportunities for focused, sustained reading practice, leading to lower proficiency in reading comprehension and analysis.

Lastly, there is a significant relationship between tablet and writing skills of the respondents. Tablets and other similar gadgets can increase learners engagement and motivation in writing tasks. The interactive nature of these devices allows for a more dynamic writing process, incorporating multimedia elements and applications that facilitate creativity. Baker et al. (2020) integrating digital tools like tablets can positively influence learners engagement and writing performance. Tablets can facilitate collaborative writing experiences, where pupils can work together on writing activities in real time, sharing ideas and providing peer feedback. This collaboration can enhance their writing skill through social interaction and shared learning experiences. Higgins et al. (2019) found that using tablets for collaborative writing tasks fostered better communication and teamwork among learners to higher-quality writing outcomes. Tablets provide access to a wealth of writing resources, including e-books, articles, and writing prompts, which can enhance the learning experience and expand learners' knowledge and vocabulary. Miller and Sweeney (2020) highlighted that learners who utilized tablets for writing assignments had greater access to diverse sources and tools, positively impacting their writing quality and depth of content.

Table 10: Significant Relationship between the Available Reading Materials of the Respondents and their Level of Macro Skills

Available Reading Materials	Listening	Speaking	Reading	Writing
Atlas	-.360*	-0.101	-0.041	0.159
Almanac	0.076	-0.205	0.084	-0.012
Dictionary	0.125	-0.126	0.138	0.062
Thesaurus	-0.016	-0.233	-0.111	0.151
Magazine	-0.044	0.181	-0.199	-0.022
Newspaper	-0.200	-0.030	-0.058	0.231
Encyclopedia	-0.050	0.131	-0.097	0.012

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

As indicated in table 10, it shows that there is an inverse relationship between the available reading material specifically atlas and listening skill of the respondents. It indicates that respondents who have atlas in their home are poor in listening skills. According to the study of Jones and Moffett (2020), it compares the effects of digital and print reading materials like atlas on learners cognitive skills which include the listening. The result shows that learners who are frequently using print-based materials, such as atlases, tended to rely on their visual learning processes. This reduces the ability of the learners to concentrate on auditory tasks.

CHAPTER FOUR CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A. Conclusions

➤ *From the findings the following conclusion were drawn:*

- On the profile of the respondents, female respondents are more dominant than male respondents. Even though respondents are not equally divided or unequal gender representations does not significantly affect the development of language macroskills of respondents. In terms of educational attainment of parents, higher education levels of parents affects the development of macroskills of their children. Parents having higher education levels can give better literacy to their children. On the otherhand, parents having lower educational attainment showed less development in macroskills of their children. Respondents having varied gadgets in their home support the development of their macroskills. The relationship between the available gadgets and skills development depends on factors such as the type of gadgets, usage patterns and the way it is used. Reading materials contribute also to the development of the macroskills of the respondents. Quality reading materials support the development of their macroskills.
- The listening and reading skills of the respondents obtained a descriptive rating of “excellent”.
- In terms of speaking skills, 24 respondents achieved a descriptive rating of “very good” while 25 respondents achieved a descriptive rating of “excellent”. Respondents got an above-average scores in speaking skills.
- In writing skills, 19 respondents achieved a descriptive rating of “very good” while the remaining 30 respondents have achieved the descriptive rating of “excellent”. Respondents got an above-average scores in writing skills.
- Overall, the respondents are good in their macroskills – listening, speaking, reading and writing skills.
- As to profile of the respondents, gender has a significant relationship with the speaking skills of the respondents. Aside from the gender, both mother and father educational attainment has significant relationship with the writing skills of the respondents.
- As to available gadgets, basic cellphone has an inverse relationship with speaking skills of the respondents. Smartphone has inverse relationship with listening and reading skills of the respondents. Lastly, tablet has an inverse relationship with the writing skills of the respondents.
- As to available reading materials, atlas has an inverse relationship with writing skills of the respondents.

B. Recommendations

➤ *In light of the conclusions drawn from the study, the following recommendations are hereby recommended:*

- Teacher must provide more guidance to the parents especially in developing the macroskills of the learners. Parents or any member of the family should provide an ample time to the learners to guide them and teach them at home.
- Teacher should create and implement more learning interventions in order to help those learners who are struggling in developing their macroskills. Teachers should continue giving and providing learners enrichment activities to further develop their skills in listening, speaking, reading and writing.
- Grade five teachers shall continue to develop professionally by attending seminars and trainings that relevant to the development of the macroskills of the grade five learners. Teachers must address immediately the learning difficulties of learners to avoid worst cases that could result on learning disorders.

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➤ ELECTRONIC SOURCES

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➤ MEMORANDUM/ ORDER

- [186]. DepEd Memorandum No. 173, s. 2019
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APPENDIX A

Request Letter to the Schools Division Superintendent

June 18, 2024

DR. JOEL B. LOPEZ, CESO IV
Schools Division Superintendent
Schools Division of Ilocos Sur
Bantay, Ilocos Sur

Sir:
Greetings!

The undersigned is conducting a study entitled “MACROSKILLS OF GRADE FIVE LEARNERS IN SELECTED SCHOOLS OF SANTA MARIA DISTRICT” in partial fulfillment of the degree Master of Arts in Education (MAEd) at Ilocos Sur Polytechnic State College, Santa Maria, Ilocos Sur.

In this regard, may I request for a permission to conduct a survey among the respondents of my study which are the Grade Five learners of Nalvo Elementary School, Bia-o Elementary School and Danuman Elementary School of Santa Maria District, Schools Division of Ilocos Sur. Rest assured that the data to be gathered will be treated with utmost confidentiality and will be solely for the purpose of the said study.

Thank you very much.

Very truly yours,

(SGD) ELVIN JAKE R. EMPLEO
Researcher

Noted:

(SGD) JOCELYN L. ABSOLOR, EdD
Dean, Graduate School/ Adviser

Approved:

(SGD) JOEL B. LOPEZ, CESO IV
Schools Division Superintendent

APPENDIX B

Indorsement Letter of EPS in-Charge of the Santa Maria District to the Schools Division Superintendent

Republic of the Philippines
Department of Education
REGION I
SCHOOLS DIVISION OF ILOCOS SUR
SANTA MARIA DISTRICT

1st Indorsement

Respectfully forwarded to the Schools Division Superintendent, Schools Division of Ilocos Sur, Bantay, Ilocos Sur, the herein request of Mr. ELVIN JAKE R. EMPLEO, Teacher III of Danuman Elementary School, to float questionnaires relative to the completion of his research entitled “Macroskills of Grade Five Learners in Selected Schools of Santa Maria District”, recommending favorable action and approval to the aforementioned.

(SGD) DR. CECILIA SALDUA
EPS in MAPEH, SDO Personnel in-Charge of Santa Maria District

APPENDIX C

Request Letter to the the Validators

June 18, 2024

Dear Validator:

Greetings in the Name of the Lord!

The undersigned is in the process of conducting a research study entitled “**Macroskills of Grade Five Learner in Selected Schools of Santa Maria District**” as a partial requirement for the degree Master of Arts in Education major in Educational Management at Ilocos Sur Polytechnic State College, Main Campus, Santa Maria, Ilocos Sur.

In connection to this, the Graduate Thesis Review Committee would like a group of experts to validate the “Questionnaire-checklist and Survey Questionnaire” to ensure the validity of test and interview questions that will be used in this study.

Your expert judgement will be considered important and helpful in determining the validity of the instrument, so that it will serve the best purpose for which it is constructed.

Thank you very much for your selfless help and support along this endeavor.

Respectfully yours,
(SGD) ELVIN JAKE R. EMPLEO
Researcher

Noted:
(SGD) JOCELYN L. ABSOLOR, EdD
Adviser/ Dean, College of Graduate Studies

APPENDIX D

Validators Form for the Research Instrument

Name: _____

Position: _____

Agency/ School: _____

Please specify your assessment in the attached Checklist and Survey Questionnaire by placing check mark (/) in the columns corresponding to your assessment.

- 5 – Strongly Agree (SA)
- 4 – Agree (A)
- 3 – Undecided (U)
- 2 – Disagree (D)
- 1 – Strongly Disagree (SD)

CRITERIA	1	2	3	4	5
The items included in the assessment instrument completely evaluate the learners' macroskills: Listening Skill Speaking Skill Reading Skill Writing Skill					
The questionnaire checklist corresponds to the survey questionnaire.					
The activities are simple, measurable, attainable, realistic and time bound.					
The activities are organized and clearly relate to the enhancement of literacy level of respondents.					
The items are clearly stated in such a way that it warrants honest answers from the respondents.					

Suggestions/ Recommendations:

Thank you very much.

Evaluator's Signature

APPENDIX E

Profile of the Validators

➤ **VALIDATORS:**

- Name: Jasmin N. Dasargo
Position: Principal II
Agency Office: Silag-Pacang Integrated School
Educational Attainment: Doctoral Degree
- Name: Glenn D. Dollente
Position: Master Teacher II
Agency/ Office: Bia-o Elementary School
Educational Attainment: Doctoral Degree
- Name: Ma. Ascencion D. Degracia
Position: Master Teacher II
Agency: Office: Laslasong Elementary School
Educational Attainment: Masteral Degree
- Name: Sharon A. Castillo
Position: Master Teacher I
Agency/ Office: Danuman Elementary School
Educational Attainment: Masteral Degree
- Name: Roel D. Dait
Position: Master Teacher I
Agency/ Office: Nalvo Elementary School
Educational Attainment: Masteral Degree

APPENDIX F

Letter to Conduct Reliability Test

August 6, 2024

MADelyn S. DATO
Teacher III/ Officer in-Charge
Suso Elementary School
Suso, Santa Maria, Ilocos Sur

Madam:

The undersigned is currently undertaking a research study entitled “**Macroskills of Grade Five Learners in Selected Schools of Santa Maria District**” in compliance with the requirements for the degree in Master of Arts in Education at Ilocos Sur Polytechnic State College, Santa Maria Campus, Santa Maria, Ilocos Sur.

In this regard, the undersigned earnestly request your generous assistance in this endeavor by allowing him to conduct pilot testing to Grade Five pupils of Suso Elementary School for his to establish reliability and validity of her research instrument.

Your approval of this request will be highly valued and appreciated.

God bless and thank you very much!

Respectfully yours,

(SGD) ELVIN JAKE R. EMPLEO
Researcher

Noted:

(SGD) JOCELYN L. ABSOLOR, EdD
Adviser/ Dean, College of Graduate Studies

APPENDIX G

Request Letter to the Respondent

June 18, 2024

Dear Respondent,

I am conducting research entitled “**Macroskills of Grade Five Learners in Selected Schools of Santa Maria District**” in compliance with the requirements for the degree in Master of Arts in Education at Ilocos Sur Polytechnic State College, Santa Maria Campus, Santa Maria, Ilocos Sur.

In this regard, may I request to share your precious time in answering the questionnaires that are necessary for the completion of the said study. Be rest assured that all the gathered information will be handled with utmost confidentiality and will be used for research purposes only.

Thank you very much and I sincerely look forward to your wholehearted cooperation in my request.

May God bless you always!

Very truly yours,

(SGD) ELVIN JAKE R. EMPLEO

Researcher

Noted:

(SGD) JOCELYN L. ABSOLOR, EdD

Adviser/ Dean, College of Graduate Studies

APPENDIX H

The Reasearch Instrument and Questionnaires

This questionnaire contains two parts. Part I will inquire about respondent’s profile. Part II will evaluate the level of respondent on their macroskills.

A. Part I. Pupil’s Profile

Name (Optional): _____

Age: _____

School: _____

(Please check the circle)

➤ Gender

Male

Female

➤ Educational Attainment of Mother

EdD/PhD

MA/MS with Doctoral units

MA/MS Degree

College Graduate with MA/ MS units

College Graduate

High School Graduate

Elementary Graduate

➤ Educational Attainment of Father

EdD/PhD

MA/MS with Doctoral units

MA/MS Degree

College Graduate with MA/ MS units

College Graduate

High School Graduate

Elementary Graduate

➤ *Available Gadgets*

- Basic cellphone
- Smartphone
- Tablet
- Desktop computer
- Laptop
- others (please specify _____)

➤ *Available Reading Materials*

- Atlas
- Almanac
- Dictionary
- Thesaurus
- Magazine
- Newspaper
- Encyclopedia
- others (please specify _____)

B. Part Ii. Macroskills➤ *LISTENING SKILL*• *Listening Activity*

Directions: Listen carefully to the story of Freddy the Frog and his quest to find his lunch to be played in a speaker twice. As you listen, pay attention to the details and the adventures Freddy encounters along the way. After you've listened to the story, you're going to answer the following questions. Write your answers on the space provided for.

- _____ 1. Who is the main character in the story?
- _____ 2. Describe it.
- _____ 3. Where did the story take place?
- _____ 4. Why did he feel hungry?
- _____ 5. Who did he meet along the way?
- _____ 6. Soon, what did he find in the forest?
- _____ 7. What did he use to catch the bug?
- _____ 8. What was the bug for?
- _____ 9. What did Freddy the Frog enjoy for his lunch?
- _____ 10. Describe Freddy's lunch in Freddy's words.

➤ *SPEAKING SKILL*

Your class will be grouped into small groups with three members. Each group will retell the story in three parts: beginning, middle and end. Each member of the group will have a part in the retelling of the story and will be given an individual score based on his/ her performance. Each group is allowed to retell the story of Freddy the Frog in their own creative way.

➤ *READING SKILL*

You will be reading the story "Frog's Lunch" twice. Each of you will read the story orally and silently. After reading the story, you are ask to answer the following questions. Encircle the letter of the correct answer.

FROG'S LUNCH

One day, a frog sat on a lily pad, still as a rock. A fish swam by. "Hello, Mr. Frog! What are you waiting for?" "I am waiting for my lunch," said the frog. "Oh, good luck!" said the fish and swam away. Then, a duck waddled by. "Hello, Mr. Frog! What are you waiting for?" "I am waiting for my lunch," said the frog. "Oh, good luck!" said the duck and waddled away. Then a bug came buzzing by. "Hello, Mr. Frog! What are you doing?" asked the bug. "I'm having my lunch! Slurp!" said the frog. Mr. Frog smiled.

Questions:

➤ *What is the title of the story?*

- Fish Lunch
- Bug's Lunch
- Frog's Lunch
- Duck's Lunch

➤ *Where does the story happen?*

- in a rock
- in a pond
- in the sea
- in the mountain

➤ *Who is the main character in the story?*

- the bug
- the fish
- the frog
- the duck

➤ *What was the frog doing?*

- resting on a lily pad
- chatting with a bug
- hunting for his food
- waiting for the rain

➤ *In what way was the frog able to get his lunch?*

- He was able to fool the bug.
- He was able to fool the fish.
- He was able to fool the rock.
- He was able to fool the duck.

➤ *Why should the frog be "still as a rock?"*

- so that he can catch his lunch
- so that the fish will say nice things about him
- so that he will not scare the other animals away
- so that the other animals will think he is friendly

➤ *What happened to the bug?*

- The bug fly away.
- The frog eat the bug.
- The bug is not harmed.
- The bug stay and talk to other animals.

➤ Which of these words describe the duck?

- careful
- curious
- eager
- patient

➤ Which of these words describe Mr. Frog?

- careful
- curious
- eager
- patient

➤ Which of these characteristics would have helped the bug?

- being eager
- being careful
- being curious
- being patient

C. WRITING SKILL

You will imagine being a frog looking for food in the area where he lives – pond in the forest.

Situation: On one sunny day, you find yourself very hungry! So, you waited for lunch which is a delicious bug! However, this is not just an ordinary bug! But a bug with magical surprises!

Now, your writing task is to continue the story and write the frog’s adventure with the bug. Write your answer on the space provided for.

➤ Guide Questions:

- How does the forest look like? Write down what you imagine of the forest.
- What does the frog look like? Write a name for the frog. What color is it and how big is it?
- Describe the bug. Write down what you imagine about it.
- What magical surprises can the bug do? If you were the bug what magical things will you do to avoid being eaten by the frog?
- End the story with a surprise. Write an interesting ending for the story.

FROG’S LUNCH

APPENDIX I**Rubrics for Scoring the Level of Macroskills**

Republic of the Philippines
Ilocos Sur Polytechnic State College
GRADUATE SCHOOL
 Santa Maria Campus, Sta. Maria, Ilocos Sur

Criteria	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Fair	Needs Improvement
Point	5	4	3	2	1
Listening Skills					
Comprehension (6,9)	Accurately comprehends and interprets the main ideas, details, and keypoints.	Generally comprehends the main ideas and details but may miss some keypoints.	Demonstrates basic comprehension but struggles with understanding key points.	Shows slight understanding the main ideas and details.	Shows significant difficulty in understanding the main ideas and details.
Direct response (1,5)	Provides a clear, concise and directly relevant response to the question asked, addressing all key aspects.	Offers a response that is mostly clear and relevant but may lack some depth or completeness.	Provides a response but it may be unclear, incomplete or somewhat off-topic.	Some response are unclear, irrelevant, or it lacks depth and completeness.	All of the responses are unclear and significantly lacks of depth and completeness.
Depth of understanding (4,8)	Demonstrates a deep understanding of the question, providing insightful and well-supported responses.	Shows a good understanding of the question, offering relevant details and examples.	Demonstrates a basic understanding of the question but may lack depth or clarity in the response.	Struggles to demonstrate a clear understanding of the question, resulting to incomplete response.	Shows significant difficulty in understanding of the question, resulting to vague or no response.
Creativity and critical thinking (2,10)	Integrates creative and critical thinking into the response, offering unique insights or perspectives.	Demonstrates good creativity and critical thinking but may lack consistency or originality.	Shows some attempts at creativity and critical thinking but with limited success.	Shows less in creativity and critical thinking, resulting in a response that is simplistic.	Lacks creativity and critical thinking, resulting in a response that is irrelevant or no response at all.
Response time (3,7)	Demonstrates the ability to think quickly and effectively in a given time.	Generally responds within an acceptable timeframes but may have occasional delays.	Answers questions somewhat slow.	Consistently answers question slowly.	Cannot give an accurate response to questions at a given timeframe.

Range of Scores	Descriptive Rating
41.00-50.00	Excellent
31.00-40.00	Very Good
21.00-30.00	Good
11.00-20.00	Fair
1.00-10.00	Needs Improvement

Criteria Point	Excellent 5	Very Good 4	Good 3	Fair 2	Needs Improve-ment 1
Speaking Skills					
Clarity and Pronunciation	Speak clearly with accurate pronunciation, making it easy for others to understand.	Usually speak clearly with mostly accurate pronunciation, though occasional words may need clarification.	Speak somewhat clearly, but some words may be mispronounced or unclear.	Often speak unclearly, making it difficult for others to understand.	Speak very unclearly with frequent mispronunciations, making it hard for others to follow.
Fluency and Flow	Speak fluently with a natural flow, using minimal pauses or fillers.	Generally, speak fluently, with occasional pauses or fillers that do not disrupt the flow.	Speak with some fluency but may pause or use fillers frequently, affecting the flow.	Struggle with fluency, often pausing or using fillers that disrupt the flow of speech.	Speak very hesitantly with many pauses and fillers, significantly disrupting the flow of speech.
Confidence and Volume	Speak confidently with appropriate volume, making the speech engaging and easy to hear.	Usually speak confidently with adequate volume, though may occasionally be too soft or too loud.	Speak with some confidence, but the volume may vary, affecting how well it was heard.	Often speak with low confidence and volume, making it hard for others to hear or engage with.	Speak with very little confidence and low volume, making the speech difficult to hear or follow.
Vocabulary and Language	Use a wide range of vocabulary and language appropriate to the context, making the speech rich and effective.	Generally, use appropriate vocabulary and language, though may repeat words or phrases.	Use basic vocabulary and language, which is understandable but lacks variety or sophistication.	Struggle to use appropriate vocabulary and often repeat simple words or phrases.	Use very limited or inappropriate vocabulary, making the speech difficult to understand or less effective.
Engagement and Interaction	Actively engage with the audience, respond well to feedback, and encourage interaction.	Usually engage with the audience and respond to feedback, though may not always encourage interaction.	Engage with the audience to some extent but may not always respond to feedback or encourage interaction.	Struggle to engage with the audience and rarely respond to feedback or encourage interaction.	Do not engage with the audience and fail to respond to feedback or encourage interaction.

Range of Scores	Descriptive Rating
21.00-25.00	Excellent
16.00-20.00	Very Good
11.00-15.00	Good
6.00-10.00	Fair
1.00-5.00	Needs Improvement

Criteria	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Fair	Needs Improvement
Point	5	4	3	2	1
Reading Skills					
Comprehension (3,10)	Correctly identifies all main ideas and key points in the text, providing accurate and detailed responses to quiz questions.	Correctly identifies most main ideas and key points, with minor inaccuracies in responses to quiz questions	Identifies some main ideas and key points, but responses to quiz questions show significant gaps or misunderstanding.	Struggles to identify some main ideas and key points, with some responses to quiz questions being incorrect or incomplete	Difficult to identify main ideas and key points with most responses to quiz questions are incorrect.
Detail Recognition (1,2)	Accurately recalls and explains specific details and facts, with occasional minor errors in quiz responses.	Generally recalls and explains specific details and facts, with occasional minor errors in quiz responses.	Recalls some details and facts but often misses or inaccurately explains key information in quiz responses.	Struggles to recall or explain specific details and facts, with some quiz responses lacking relevant information.	Difficult to recall and explain specific detail and facts, with most quiz responses lacking relevant information.
Vocabulary and Contextual Understanding (4,8,9)	Demonstrates an excellent understanding of vocabulary, including the ability to infer the meaning of unfamiliar words from context, accurately reflected in quiz responses.	Shows a good understanding of the vocabulary and can infer most meanings from context, with minor errors in quiz responses.	Shows a basic understanding of vocabulary, with limited ability to infer meanings from context, leading to frequent errors in quiz responses.	Struggles with vocabulary understanding and inference from context, resulting in some errors in quiz responses.	Difficult with vocabulary understanding and inference from context resulting to numerous errors in quiz responses.
Inferential Reasoning (5,7)	Makes insightful inferences and logical deductions about the text, accurately reflected in responses to inference-based quiz questions.	Makes reasonable inferences and logical deductions, with minor inaccuracies in responses to inference-based quiz questions.	Makes some but often with errors or oversimplifications in responses to inference-based quiz questions.	Struggles to make inferences or logical deductions with some responses to inference-based quiz questions being incorrect.	Difficult to make inferences or logical deductions with most responses to inference based questions being incorrect.
Critical Analysis and Interpretation (6)	Provides thorough and insightful analysis and interpretation of the text, demonstrating a deep understanding in quiz responses.	Provides clear and reasonable analysis and interpretation, with minor gaps or errors in quiz responses.	Provides basic analysis and interpretation, with significant gaps or simplistic reasoning in quiz responses.	Struggles to provide analysis or interpretation, with quiz responses showing little understanding of deeper meanings.	Difficult to provide analysis or interpretation with quiz responses show no understanding of deeper meanings.

Range of Scores	Descriptive Rating
41.00-50.00	Excellent
31.00-40.00	Very Good
21.00-30.00	Good
11.00-20.00	Fair
1.00-10.00	Needs Improvement

Criteria	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Fair	Needs Improvement
Point	5	4	3	2	1
Writing Skills					
Content and Ideas	The writing consistently presents clear, original, and well-developed ideas with strong supporting details.	The writing generally presents clear and well-developed ideas with adequate supporting details.	The writing presents basic ideas that are somewhat clear, with some supporting details, but lacks depth.	The writing presents underdeveloped ideas that are unclear, with minimal or irrelevant supporting details.	The writing lacks clear ideas, is disorganized, and has little to no supporting details.
Organization and Structure	The writing is consistently well-organized with a logical structure, clear introduction, body, and conclusion, and smooth transitions between ideas.	The writing is generally well-organized with a clear structure and effective transitions, though minor improvements could be made.	The writing has a basic structure with some organization but may have weak transitions or lack a clear progression of ideas.	The writing is poorly organized, with a confusing structure and limited transitions between ideas.	The writing is disorganized with no clear structure, making it difficult to follow the writer's ideas.
Grammar and Mechanics	The writing is consistently free of grammatical, spelling, and punctuation errors.	The writing has few minor errors in grammar, spelling, or punctuation that do not interfere with meaning.	The writing contains some errors in grammar, spelling, or punctuation that occasionally interfere with meaning.	The writing has frequent errors in grammar, spelling, or punctuation that often interfere with meaning.	The writing is filled with errors in grammar, spelling, and punctuation, making it difficult to understand.
Vocabulary and word Choice	The writing consistently uses varied, precise, and effective vocabulary appropriate to the audience and purpose.	The writing generally uses appropriate and effective vocabulary with some variation and precision.	The writing uses basic vocabulary that is generally appropriate but lacks variety or precision.	The writing uses limited or inappropriate vocabulary, often repeating words or using imprecise language.	The writing uses poor or incorrect vocabulary, making the meaning unclear.
Style and Voice	The writing consistently reflects a strong, distinct voice and style that is engaging and appropriate for the audience and purpose.	The writing generally reflects a clear voice and style that is appropriate for the audience and purpose.	The writing has a basic voice and style but may be inconsistent or lack distinctiveness.	The writing has a weak or inconsistent voice and style that is not well-suited to the audience or purpose.	The writing lacks a clear voice and style, making it unengaging or inappropriate for the audience and purpose.

Range of Scores	Descriptive Rating
21.00-25.00	Excellent
16.00-20.00	Very Good
11.00-15.00	Good
6.00-10.00	Fair
1.00-5.00	Needs Improvement